

RESEARCH ROADMAP

(Description file)

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Research roadmap

Description of the steps of the roadmap

1. Sustainability baseline definition

This initial phase marks the first interaction between the researcher and the company. It follows the principle that “if you can’t measure it, you can’t improve it”, a concept widely attributed to Peter Drucker. The goal is to establish a clear sustainability baseline by identifying, selecting, and calculating relevant sustainability indicators. This baseline serves as the reference point for assessing improvements as the company adjusts its production scheduling to enhance sustainability.

Objective

Establish a baseline for sustainability performance.

Key activities and tasks

- Select a sustainability assessment framework if the company does not already have one.
- Gather process and operational data from the company.
- Calculate the indicators.

Information required

- Production data, energy usage reports, waste management records, labor reports, financial cost data, etc.

Supporting tools and frameworks

- Sustainable production principles (Viles et al., 2023).
- Indicator frameworks being used in the literature: SDGs, GRI, ISO 14031, Circular Economy Metrics, etc.

Provided templates:

- Sustainable Production Indicators (list).

Company input

- Providing existing indicators, data for new indicator calculation, reports, etc.

2. Analysis of the production process

This step aims to develop a clear understanding of the production system's structure, constraints, and operational logic. It guides the research in gathering the necessary knowledge to accurately model and improve the scheduling process.

Objective

Develop a clear understanding of how the production system operates, including its structure, constraints, sequencing logic, and decision-making processes.

Key activities and tasks

- Define the scope of the analysis:
 - Workstation level (a single machine or workstation where one job is processed at a time).
 - Manufacturing cell level (a group of interconnected workstations that process a family of jobs).
 - Production line level (a sequential flow of machines and workstations that handle a defined set of jobs).
 - Production plant level (a full factory or plant that includes multiple production lines, workstations, and support processes).
 - Company-wide level (all production plants and warehouses within a company, integrating scheduling across multiple locations).
 - Supply chain level (scheduling across suppliers, manufacturers, distributors, and customers in a global network).
- Classify the production system (Lopez & Roubellat, 2001):
 - Single machine
 - Parallel machines
 - Job shop
 - Flow shop
 - Cellular manufacturing
 - Batch processing
 - Hybrid systems
 - Other
- Identify production constraints (for a more detailed description of commonly used constraints see Akbar & Irohara (2018):
 - Machine-related constraints:
 - Machine availability and capacity
 - Preventive maintenance schedules
 - Job constraints:
 - Prioritization rules
 - Job dependency constraints
 - Set-up constraints
 - Workforce constraints:
 - Operator-machine assignments
 - Shift structures and handovers
 - Level of manual interventions required in the process
- Define how unexpected scenarios are handled:
 - Machine failures and downtime management
 - Urgency orders and rush jobs
 - Unplanned events
- Define the simplifications that will be made in the model.

Information required

- Job data: Number of jobs, processing times, job routing, setup times, job dependencies, priority rules.
- Machine data: Number and types of machines, availability, maintenance schedules, failure logs, setup constraints, parallel processing capabilities.
- Workforce data: Number of operators, shift schedules, operator-machine assignments, manual vs. automated tasks, workload distribution.
- Scheduling and execution data: Current scheduling method, historical schedules vs. actual execution, causes of delays, and system performance metrics (OEE, utilization, throughput).
- Material and resource constraints: Raw material availability, lead times, storage limitations, and material movement constraints.

Supporting tools and frameworks

Process flow diagrams, Value Stream Mapping, Input-output analysis, etc.

Provided templates

- None.

Company input

- Providing information about the production process.

3. Identification of areas of improvement

This step focuses on identifying aspects of the production system that can be improved through scheduling to enhance sustainability.

Objective

Identify potential areas of improvement within the production system that can be influenced through scheduling.

Key activities and tasks

- Select sustainability indicators relevant to the company (from step 1) keeping in mind the Triple-Bottom Line (economic, environmental and social aspects).
- Identify scheduling-related areas of improvement by analyzing the production process.
 - Examine how job sequencing, machine allocation, and workforce scheduling affect each selected indicator.
 - Identify constraints that impact sustainability performance (e.g., bottlenecks, inefficient setups, unbalanced workload).
 - Establish specific production system aspects that could be improved via scheduling to enhance sustainability performance.
 - Examples:
 - Reducing changeovers → Less waste, lower energy use.

- Balancing operator workload → Lower ergonomic risks, improved worker satisfaction.
- Optimizing machine assignments → Higher utilization, reduced idle time.
- Sequencing jobs based on material compatibility → Minimized raw material waste.
- Ensure each area of improvement has a direct connection to a sustainability indicator.

Information required

- Data from step 1 and step 2.

Supporting tools and frameworks

- Ranking methods to rank improvement areas (for example: Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis).
- Root Cause Analysis to determine key scheduling inefficiencies (for example: Ishikawa Diagram).

Provided templates

- Example of mapping a company's areas of interactions.

Company input

- Providing information, selecting indicators to improve, and giving ideas on how to improve them.

4. Problem formulation

This step translates identified areas of improvement into concrete scheduling goals and englobes the formulation of the problem.

Objective

Formulate the optimization problem.

Key activities and tasks

- Review literature on scheduling problem formulations and sustainable objectives to understand existing approaches and define the problem accordingly.
- Determine the appropriate modeling approach, if applicable (for an exhaustive list, see Guzman et al. (2022)):
 - Binary Programming
 - Constraint Programming
 - Dynamic Programming
 - Fuzzy Programming
 - Goal Programming
 - Integer Programming
 - Linear Programming

- Integer linear Programming
- Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP)
- Mixed Integer Non-Linear Programming (MILP)
- Multi-Objective Linear Programming (MOLP)
- Multi-Objective Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MOMILP)
- Etc.
- Select the optimization strategy:
 - Weighted Sum Approach: Assign different weights to each objective and sum them into a single function.
 - Pareto Front Optimization: Generate a set of non-dominated solutions instead of a single best solution.
 - Lexicographic Approach: Prioritize objectives hierarchically.
 - Etc.
- Formulate the problem:
 - Define objective functions.
 - Identify decision variables.
 - Specify constraints.
- Check or test the correctness of the model.
 - Ensure that the selected formulation is computationally solvable.
 - Identify any potential computational complexity issues (e.g., problem size, solving time).
 - Check if simplifications or relaxations are needed.

Information required

- Data from previous steps
- Sample data for testing (optional)

Supporting tools and frameworks

- Modeling libraries and programming tools (e.g., Pyomo, PuLP, JuMP, Python, R, Excel) for structuring the optimization problem and verifying its logic.

Provided templates

- List of commonly used sustainability scheduling objectives (Cavallieri et al., 2024).

Company input

- None.

5. Problem resolution

After formulating the scheduling problem, this step guides the researcher through problem resolution and validation. It focuses on selecting the optimization

strategy and solution approach to generate, validate, and refine a set of solutions before selecting the most suitable ones for implementation.

Objective

Select an optimization approach and solve the formulated scheduling problem.

Key activities and tasks

- Select the solution approach (for an exhaustive list refer to Guzman et al. (2022)):
 - Optimizer Algorithms: Exact methods such as Branch and Bound, Branch and Cut, and Simplex.
 - Heuristic Algorithms: Problem-specific heuristics like Greedy, Relax-and-Fix, and Benders Decomposition.
 - Metaheuristic Algorithms: Generalized search strategies including Genetic Algorithm, GRASP, Simulated Annealing, and Tabu Search.
 - Matheuristic Algorithms: Hybrid approaches combining heuristics/metaheuristics with mathematical models, such as GA + Mathematical Model or Simulated Annealing + Mathematical Model.
- Implement the optimization model:
 - Implement the solution approach.
 - Configure solver parameters and optimization settings.
 - Encode all constraints, objectives, and decision variables.
- Refine the model.
 - Test with small datasets to check feasibility and logic
 - Compare solutions with real production data and/or benchmark algorithms
 - Adjust constraints or parameters to improve performance
- Solve the scheduling problem
 - Execute the selected optimization approach with real production data.
 - If using a multi-objective approach, generate a set of feasible solutions (e.g., Pareto front, weighted sum results).
 - Ensure all scheduling constraints are satisfied.
- Analyze and interpret results
 - Compare different solutions based on sustainability and operational indicators.
 - Evaluate trade-offs between conflicting objectives (e.g., sustainability vs. cost).
 - Validate results with company stakeholders.
- Conduct sensitivity or scenario analysis (optional)
 - Evaluate the impact of changes in key algorithm parameters.
 - Test how different scenarios affect scheduling outcomes.

Information required

- Real production data (job processing times, constraints, resource availability).
- Historical scheduling data for validation and benchmarking.

Supporting tools and frameworks

- Optimization solvers (Gurobi, CPLEX, SCIP, CBC, GLPK).
- Heuristic/metaheuristic libraries (DEAP, OR-Tools, Simulated Annealing, Tabu Search).
- Mathematical and modeling tools (Pyomo, JuMP, MATLAB Optimization Toolbox).
- Simulation tools (AnyLogic, FlexSim, SimPy, Simul8, Arena).
- Multi-objective optimization frameworks (PlatEMO, NSGA-II, MOEA Framework).
- Benchmarking and sensitivity analysis (Monte Carlo simulations, statistical validation).
- Decision-support tools (TOPSIS, AHP, Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis).
- Visualization and reporting (Matplotlib, Seaborn, Power BI, Tableau, Excel).

Provided templates

- None.

Company input

- Validate schedule feasibility: Ensure alignment with operational constraints and workforce limitations.
- Assess solution quality: Review scheduling outcomes based on key performance indicators.
- Provide feedback on trade-offs: evaluate sustainability, efficiency, and cost considerations.
- Test implementation feasibility: Conduct pilot runs or simulations to verify practicality.
- Support data validation: Ensure input data accurately represents real production conditions.
- Participate in solution selection: Compare and choose the best scheduling approach.
- Identify operational challenges: Highlight overlooked constraints or inefficiencies.

6. Sustainability reassessment

This final step evaluates how the optimized scheduling schemes impact the targeted sustainability indicators. It assesses improvements through simulations, data analysis, and comparisons with baseline performance to ensure alignment with sustainability goals.

Objective

Evaluate how the optimized scheduling scheme(s) can impact the selected sustainability indicators.

Key activities and tasks

- Estimate sustainability enhancement based on the solution(s) obtained:
 - Extract key scheduling outputs from Step 5.
 - Map each scheduling improvement to its corresponding sustainability indicator from steps 1 and 3.
 - Estimate sustainability enhancements:
 - Simulation-based estimation: running the optimized schedule in a simulated environment.
 - Analytical estimation: using mathematical models to extrapolate improvements.
 - Comparison with historical data: evaluating whether the optimized schedule would have performed better than past schedules.
- Compare baseline vs. optimized scheduling results:
 - Baseline: Pre-optimization scheduling data or theoretical reference case.
 - Optimized: New scheduling model outputs.
- Discuss research limitations and practical implementation
- Align improvements with the SDGs (optional)

Information required

- Indicators from steps 1 and 3.
- Optimized solutions from step 5.

Supporting tools and frameworks

- Data analysis and visualization tools for assessing trends and visualizing scheduling impacts (Excel, Power BI, Tableau, Matplotlib, Seaborn).
- Statistical analysis tools for comparing baseline vs. optimized scheduling results (R, Python Statsmodels, SPSS).
- Simulation tools to simulate real-world scheduling performance (AnyLogic, FlexSim, Tecnomatix, SimPy).
- Benchmarking tools to assess improvements against past schedules. (Monte Carlo simulations, historical data comparison).

Provided templates

- Link between sustainable production indicators and SDG (Viles et al., 2023).

Company input

- Validation and analysis of improvements.
- Provide operational feedback.
- Support impact estimations.

- Align results with strategic goals.
- Identify potential refinements.

Provided templates

Step 1: Sustainable Production Indicators (Viles et al., 2023)

Principle	Nº	Indicator	Description	Value	Units	Trend
(1) Design for circularity.	1	Include the concept of sustainability and circularity among the criteria for design	Scale (1-3) where: 1 – sustainability and circularity criteria are not included among the criteria for design; 2 – sustainability and circularity criteria are partially included among the criteria for design; 3 – sustainability and circularity criteria are completely included among the criteria for design		#	
	2	Non-renewable virgin material	kg of non-renewable virgin material used as input for the production/kg of material used as input for the production		%	
	3	Products designed for disassembly, reuse, or recycling	Number of products designed for disassembly, reuse, or recycling/Total number of products		%	
	4	Packaging designed for disassembly, reuse, or recycling	Number of packaging designed for disassembly, reuse, or recycling/Total number of packaging		%	
	5	Material used	Kg of material used for production per unit of product. The following materials should be included: raw materials natural resources, associated process materials (materials that are needed for the manufacturing process but are not part of the final product), semi-manufactured goods or parts (including all forms of materials and components other than raw materials that are part of the final product) and materials for packaging purposes.		kg/un	
	6	Energy consumed from renewable sources	kWh of energy from renewable sources consumed/kWh of energy consumed		%	
	7	Fresh water consumption	Amount of fresh water consumption used/Total amount of water consumed		%	
(2) Conserve resources and preserve their value.	8	Connections between companies for Industrial Symbiosis	Number of companies with which an exchange of waste or by-product to be used as input is carried out		#	
	9	Energy intensity	Absolute energy consumption (kWh)/Revenues (€)		kWh/€	
	10	Water on-site circulation (recycle and reuse)	$(Q \text{ water use} - Q \text{ total water withdrawal})/Q \text{ total water withdrawal}$		%	
(3) Manage waste sustainably.	11	Waste sent to landfill	Kg of waste sent to landfill/Kg of waste generated		%	
	12	Waste recycled and reused	Kg of waste recycled and reused/Kg of waste generated		%	

	13	Wastewater production	Wastewater production/Total number of products produced		m ³ /u n	
(4) Pursue a risk-free environment.	14	GHG emissions	GHG emissions should ideally be calculated following the GHG protocol or other recognized standards		Ton CO ₂ e q	
	15	Hazardous/harmful/toxic materials	Kg of hazardous/harmful/toxic materials (to be identified by each company) used/consumed/emitted		kg	
(5) Prioritize employees' well-being.	16	Job satisfaction	Number of employees who report complete job satisfaction (based on a questionnaire) where physical, functional, and psychological aspects are considered/Total number of employees		%	
	17	Turnover rate	Number of employees who leave during a period /Average number of employees in the period		%	
	18	Lost workday injury and illness case rate (LWDII)	(Number of recordable injuries and/or illnesses in one year/Total number of hours worked by all employees in one year) x 200.000. The 200.000 is calculated considering 100 employees that work 40 hours per week 50 weeks a year. It indicates the number of injuries or illnesses per 100 full-time workers.		#	
(6) Enhance management commitment to sustainability.	19	Annual operating costs	Annual operating costs/Revenues		%	
	20	The extent to which voluntary environmental management systems are implemented	Scale (1–3) where: 1 – no voluntary environmental management systems are implemented; 2 – voluntary environmental management systems are implemented but there is room for improvement; 3 – voluntary environmental management systems are implemented and there is no room for improvement		#	
	21	Investments in sustainable development	Total investments for sustainable development concerning the company's business activity/Total investments		%	
	22	Women in managerial positions	Women in managerial positions/Total number of managerial positions		%	
	23	Employees' suggestions for improvements in quality, social, and EHS performance	Number of employees who made suggestions/Total number of employees		%	
	24	EHS compliance costs	Annual costs associated with EHS compliance (e.g. fines, liabilities, worker compensation, waste treatment and disposal, remediation)/Annual revenues		%	
	25	The extent to which sustainability and circularity are considered in the objectives and targets of senior leaders	Scale (1–3) where: 1 – sustainability and circularity criteria are not included in the objectives and targets of senior leaders; 2 – sustainability and circularity criteria are partially included in the objectives and targets of senior leaders; 3 – sustainability and circularity criteria are completely included in the objectives and targets of senior leaders		#	

	26	Employee training	Total hours of training for personal and professional growth/Number of employees		Hours / employee	
(7) Make a positive contribution to the community.	27	Community spending and charitable contributions	Community spending and charitable contributions with social or environmental impact/Revenues		%	
	28	Community–company partnerships	Number of community–company partnerships		#	
	29	Local employment opportunities	Number of jobs created annually for local employees, suppliers, and community		#	
	30	Company wage compared to minimum wage	Company minimum wage/minimum wage in the company’s location		%	
(8) Promote value chain stakeholder collaboration.	31	Stakeholder engagement	Scale (1–3), where: 1 – stakeholders are engaged in organizational activities such as product development, work coordination, strategy-making, decision-making, and corporate social responsibility initiatives...; 2 – stakeholders are partially engaged in organizational activities; 3 – stakeholders are completely engaged in organizational activities		#	
	32	Customer complaints and returns	Number of complaints or returns/Number of products sold		%	
	33	Products with take-back policies in place	Products with take-back policies in place/Total amount of products		%	
	34	The extent to which supplier selection is based on sustainability performance	Number of suppliers selected because of sustainability performance/Number of suppliers		%	
(9) Measure and optimize sustainable processes.	35	Productivity	Revenues/Number of employees		€/employees	
	36	Data measurement	Production processes where data measurement is done/Total number of production processes		%	
	37	Unit production cost variance	Actual unit production cost/Theoretical unit production cost – 1		%	
(10) Boost the use of sustainable technologies.	38	Investment in research and sustainable technologies	Investments in research and sustainable technologies/Total investments		%	
	39	Best Available Techniques (BAT) used	Number of BAT used within the production facilities		#	

Step 3: Mapping areas of interaction

This template helps identify and organize a company's key interaction areas, capturing not only inputs and outputs but also internal dynamics and external connections across different stakeholders or systems.

Step 4: Commonly used sustainable production objectives

This figure presents a visualization of the combinations of sustainability indicators considered in real-life case studies (Cavallieri et al., 2024). Each node represents an individual indicator, while each branch illustrates a specific combination of indicators used together in a study. The numbers along the branches indicate the frequency of each combination; branches without numbers represent combinations used only once. Nodes are color-coded by sustainability dimension: economic (blue), environmental (green), and social (orange).

MKS: Makespan; W/CU: Workload/Capacity utilization; LC: Labor cost; Q: Quality; SUT: set-up time; TRD: tardiness; P: Productivity; OC: Operating cost; IT: Idle time; B: Backlog; EC: Energy consumption; GHG: GHG emissions; PC: Power consumption; EI: Environmental impact; FWC: Freshwater consumption; W: Waste; WC: Working conditions; WH: Working hours; SB: Social benefits; S/T: Skills and Training.

Step 6: Link between SPIs and SDGs

This figure presents a five-step Sankey diagram that illustrates how the proposed sustainability indicators connect to the United Nations 2030 Agenda (Viles et al., 2023). The diagram links each indicator to its corresponding SDG indicator, SDG target, and ultimately to one or more of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). In total, the indicators can contribute to 24 SDG indicators, 28 targets, and 13 SDGs. Each flow represents a traceable relationship, starting from a sustainability principle and passing through the relevant indicator toward the global goals.

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